

Description of Family Stress Levels in Treatment of Elderly in the Village of Panggung Island, Semende Darat Marine, Muara Enim District 2019

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Abstract— Background: The family is the unity of the people involved in the marriage, blood relationship and living in one house. The presence of significant events such as family members who have elderly in a home creates stress for families who care for them so that the demands are forcing the family to be able to adapt to the in terms of allocating their time to care for the elderly. This study aims to describe the level of stress in families with elderly. This study used a descriptive exploratory method, the total 30 respondents. This research was carried out in the island stage island of Semende sub-district in the sea of Muara Enim district 2019. Using the depress in anxiety stress scales questionnaire. The results of this study indicate that most families experience mild stress 20 respondents (66.7%), whereas moderate stress there 5 respondents (16.75), who experience normal stress 4 respondents (13.3%) respondents who experience severe stress 1 respondents (3.3%). This research is expected for elderly families to further maximize their participation in providing support to families, which in turn can create a better mental life for families in increasing their knowledge and skills in providing care and activities in daily life.

Keywords— Family, stress level.

I. INTRODUCTION

The large number of elderly population in Indonesia in the future has both positive and negative impacts. Positive impact, if the elderly population is in a healthy, active and productive state. On the other hand, the large number of the elderly population becomes a burden if the elderly have a problem of declining health resulting in an increase in the cost of health services, a decrease in income / income, an increase in disability, the absence of social and environmental support that is not friendly to the elderly population. (Ministry of Health RI, 2017).

The largest population after China, India, and the United States, as well as the total population of the elderly in Indonesia also ranks fourth in the world, amounting to 20.24 million people (Susenas, 2014). In 2020 the estimated population of the elderly in Indonesia reaches 28.8 million or 11.34% with a life expectancy of around 71.1 years (Jaroch, Jaroch, & Emilia, 2017).

Indonesia is one of the Asian countries whose population growth is fast growing. Since 2000, Indonesia already has an elderly population of 14.4 million (7.18% of the population) and by 2020 it is estimated that there will be 28.8 million (11.34%). The results of data collection conducted in 20 07 found that the elderly population numbered 18.96 million (8.42% of the total population) with a composition of 9.04% women and 7.80% men (Amirzadeh, Ameneh, & Mohammadi, 2018).

Based on population projection data, it is estimated that in 2017 there will be 23.66 million (elderly people in Indonesia (9.03%). It is predicted that the number of elderly population will be in2020 (27.08 million), in 2025 (33.69 million), in

2030 (40 , 95 million) and 2035 (48.19 million) (Ministry of Health, 2017) The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) reported the number of elderly people in Indonesia in 2016 of 21.15 million people, or 8.5% of the total population with the total population of elderly women (12.78 million people) and the total population of men (8.37 million people) (Andhi & Sukmawat, 2016)

Special Region of Yogyakarta is a province that has the highest percentage of elderly people at 13.4% with 123,121 elderly (Ministry of Health RI, 2016). Bantul is a regency in the province of the Special Region of Yogyakarta which has a total of 133,397 elderly people. Pandak District is one of the Districts in Bantul Regency, which has a population of 23,215 people. Triharjo Village is a village in Pandak District with a population of 12,288 with 1,800 elderly people (Andhi & Sukmawat, 2016). The dependency burden figure reflects the economic burden that must be borne by the population of productive age to finance the elderly population with the assumption that the elderly population is not economically productive elderly. (Ministry of Health RI, 2017).

Family as caregiver has an important role because this is where individuals can grow and develop. The family is the main source of support for the elderly in the community. Care performed by the family as caregiver for the elderly is associated with stress due to functional and psychological disorders and chronic diseases experienced by the elderly (Maryam, Rosidawati, Riasmini, & Suryati, 2012). The family is the closest social environment for an individual. Likewise for the elderly. The environment near the elderly is family. The function of the family for the elderly is very important (Sri & Kamalah, 2018).

Families play a role in the implementation of nursing care practices such as preventing health problems or caring for sick family members. The family can also carry out health tasks means being able to solve health problems. The family health tasks include the task of recognizing the health development disorder of each family member, making decisions for appropriate health actions, the task of providing care to sick family members, the task of maintaining a favorable atmosphere at home for health, the task of maintaining reciprocal relationships between families and health institutions (Andhi & Sukmawat, 2016).

Family members have an important role in caring for the elderly with cognitive impairment. Caring for the elderly with cognitive impairment can lead to family supervision as a caregiver. Therefore, there is a need to conduct research on the event. (Andhi & Sukmawat, 2016). The quality of life of the elderly is good when the family can carry out its function for the elderly as a supporter and social environment for the elderly. Good family support for the elderly will improve the quality of life of the elderly (Wafroh, Herawati, & Lestari, 2017).

In the elderly there will be various setbacks in the organs of the body therefore the elderly must maintain their health by eating nutritiously balanced meals nutritional needs for the elderly (elderly) are met adequately, drinking as much as 1.5-2 liters of water a day because of water very large means for the body to carry out bodily functions, prevent the emergence of various diseases in the urinary tract such as urinary stones, kidney stones and others, regular exercise and in accordance with muscle training of elderly people (the elderly) can inhibit the rate of degenerative changes, rest that enough, maintain cleanliness, drink the necessary nutritional supplements, check health regularly, mentally and mentally calm and balanced, recreation, relationships between healthy neighbors (Mohamed, Abozed, El-damhougy, Salama, & Hussein, 2020).

Based on the data above, the authors are interested in conducting a study concerning the description of the level of family stress in caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Village, Kemende Darat Laut, Muara Enim District 2019.

II. METHOD

This type of research is a descriptive method that is a method of research conducted with the aim of researching a situation objectively. The population in this study is to all elderly families who are in the village of Pulau Pulau Stage on the Kemende Darat Laut, Muara Enim District 2019.

The sample in this study was an elderly family in the Pulau Desa area of the Semende Darat Laut District in Muara Enim Regency which was then chosen as the sample. Sampling using the incidental Sempling method, ie sampling is done on an improvised basis without pre-planned, and samples taken are 30 Respondents.

Data collected at the time of the study with interviews with the elderly used a questionnaire list and observations were made for certain questions

III. RESULTS

1. Umur

TABLE I. Characteristics of Respondents by Age in Pulau Panggung Village Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019.

Age (Years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
25	6	20.0
29	4	13.3
30	14	46.7
39	4	13.3
45	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on table I shows that the age of the respondents is known that the percentage of age who care for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019. The most is 30 years, as many as 14 people (46%), and the least is the age group of 45 years. 2 people (6%). Respondents are considered at the age of 30 years, where that age is the age of caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019.

Age Categories According to the Ministry of Health RI (2009): Early childhood = 0-5 years, Childhood = 5-11 years, Early adolescence = 12-16 years, Late adolescence = 17-25 years, Early adulthood = 26-35 years, Late adulthood = 36 - 45, Early elderly = 46-55, Late elderly = 56-65, years, Seniors = 65-above.

2. Gender

TABLE II. Characteristics of Respondents by Gender in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	2	6.7
Female	28	93.3
Total	30	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on gender, the number of samples that treat elderly elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019. With male gender of 2 people (6%) and women of 28 people (93%), this is caused by the number there are more women caring for the elderly than the number of men caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019.

3. Last education

TABLE III. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Last Education in Desa Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019.

Last Education Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
SMP	9	30.0
SMA	19	63.3
PT	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on table III shows that the last education of the Respondents is known that the percentage of the last education caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Village Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019 was the highest number of high schools (Senior High Schools) namely

19 people (63%), and the least there are 2 university (6%) and 9 people (30%) of junior high schools.

4. Respondent Jobs

TABLE IV. Characteristics Based on Respondent Job in Desa Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019.

Respondent Job	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Farmers	26	86.7
Entrepreneur	2	6.7
Government employees	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on table IV shows that the work caring for the elderly is known that the percentage of jobs in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019 the most are farmers, 26 people (86%), and the least is entrepreneurship 2 people (6%) and Government employees as much as 2 people (6%).

Distribution of Variables Researched

The level of family stress in caring for the elderly

TABLE V. Level of Family Stress in Caring for the Elderly in Pulau Panggung Village Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019.

Stress Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Normal	4	13.3
small	20	66.7
average	5	16.6
severe	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Table V shows that 20 respondents (66%) experienced mild stress, 5 respondents (16%) experienced moderate stress, 4 respondents (13%) experienced normal stress, and 1 respondent (3%) experienced severe stress.

TABLE VI. The stress level of the family caring for the elderly

Stress Level	Frequency	Gender		Family burden	Family support
		P	L		
Normal	4	4		Most of the 4 respondents who experienced normal stress only took care of the elderly and took care of one child and also the economy of the respondents was sufficient.	There is support from the respondent's family
small					
average					
average	20	18	2	Most of the 20 respondents who experienced mild stress only took care of the elderly and took care of 1-2 children.	There is support from the respondent's family
severe	5	5		Most of the 5 respondents who were experiencing stress were just looking after the elderly and taking	There is support from the respondent's family

Stress Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Family burden	Family support
1	1		care of 1-5 children.	The lack of support from the respondent's family added to the inadequate economic problems

Source: Primary Data 2019

IV. DISCUSSION

Elderly is someone who because of his age experiences biological, physical, psychological, and social changes. Entering old age means experiencing setbacks, for example physical setbacks that are characterized by sagging skin, graying hair, teeth begin to toothless, hearing is unclear, vision is getting worse, slow motion, and body figures are not proportional (Nugroho, 2008).

The results of this study indicate that the age of the respondents is known that the percentage of age caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019. The most is 30 years, as many as 14 people (46%), and the least is the age group of 45 years. 2 people (6%). Respondents are considered at the age of 30 years, which is the age of caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Village Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019, based on sex that the number of samples caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019. With gender of men as much as 2 people (6%) and women as much as 28 people (93%). This is caused because the number of women caring for the elderly is greater than the number of men caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019, it is known that the percentage of the latest education caring for the elderly in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019 the most were high school (high school), namely as many as 19 people (63%), and the least were colleges as many as 2 people (6%) and junior high school 9 people (30%). the percentage of jobs in Pulau Panggung Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019 the most were farmers, 26 people (86%), and the least were entrepreneurs 2 people (6%) and civil servants as much as 2 people (6%), and 20 respondents (66%) experienced mild stress, 5 respondents (16%) experienced moderate stress, 4 respondents (13%) experienced normal stress, and 1 respondent (3%) experienced severe stress.

The effect of stress on families caring for the elderly, namely, the amount of family burden carried, economic factors, age, and lack of support from the family. The role of the family is the family's actions and acceptance of the sick patient. The family consists of husband, wife, children and for Indonesia can expand to include relatives from both parties stating that the family functions as a role system for its members, always ready to provide help and assistance if needed. Meanwhile, the role of the family in protecting the elderly greatly determines the survival of the elderly, where the elderly need economic support to meet their basic needs.

As well as requiring social moral support to deal with his aging age and overcome his boredom in the old mass. The role of the family is also needed when the elderly face diseases that carry as a result of aging, this role is related to the function of the family as a maintenance function where the family basically has an obligation to nurture members who are sick, suffering, and elderly (Sri & Kamalah, 2018).

Stress is the body's response that is not specific to any needs of the body that are disturbed, a universal phenomenon that occurs in everyday life and cannot be avoided, everyone experiences it, stress members have a total impact on the individual that is on the physical, psychological, intellectual, social and spiritually, stress can threaten physiological balance. Emotional stress can cause negative feelings towards yourself and others. Intellectual stress will disrupt a person's perception and ability to solve problems, social stress will disrupt an individual's relationship to life (Mohamed et al., 2020).

The level of stress that there are levels of stress mild, moderate, and severe and as for the factors that influence stress that is from within and within the family, the existence of significant events such as family members caring for the elderly in one home creates stress conditions for the family who take care of him so that it becomes a tutelage that forces the family to be able to adapt to changes in terms of dividing the time to care for the elderly (Mohammed & Abdullah, 2020).

V. CONCLUSION

Family characteristics in the care of the elderly in Pulau Pangung Village Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019 are female and male, aged 25-45 years, educated in junior high school, high school and university, the majority of respondents work as farmers

Stress Level Families who care for the elderly in Pulau Pangung Village, Semende Darat Laut Sub-District Muara Enim District 2019 mostly experience mild stress.

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